

A Summary of the Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite (UARS)

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Abstract -- The UARS satellite has been operating for six years and has gathered an unprecedented amount of data on the stratosphere. The most significant findings from UARS are associated with the mapping of the polar ozone depletions and the observations of the long term trends in chlorine gases in the stratosphere.

aboard the Shuttle Discovery. UARS is considered as the first of the Mission to Planet Earth series of NASA spacecraft. As of this writing, (mid 1997), UARS is still operating well beyond its original mission lifetime of 18 months. Of the original 10 instruments, 8 are still operational (see Table).

INTRODUCTION

In the early 1980's, following the success of the Nimbus 7, NASA proposed to develop and launch a more comprehensive satellite mission to understand the chemistry and physics of the stratosphere. Nimbus 7 instrumentation had focused on the stratospheric nitrogen species, and it was realized that critical chlorine species would need to be measured as well. At that time, before the discovery of the ozone hole, atmospheric chemical models were predicting that the first signals of CFC driven ozone loss would appear in the mid-stratosphere (30-40 km). This region is too high to be accessible by aircraft. High altitude balloons had made measurements in this region, but the high altitude balloons cannot provide a global - seasonal picture of the evolving chemistry of the mid-stratosphere since they can only be launched from the southern US during early late spring and early fall.

After studying a number of options, the Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite (UARS) was developed with intended launch in the late 1980's. The suite of instruments included measurements of all the important components of the chlorine and nitrogen radicals, source gases and long lived tracers. UARS was also designed to measure the solar UV flux with unprecedented precision and to estimate the energetic particle input from outer space. (Energetic particles can generate large quantities of nitrogen oxide which destroys ozone in the mesosphere and upper stratosphere.) Finally, UARS included two novel direct wind measurement instruments to improve our understanding of the stratospheric dynamics. Table 1 summarizes the UARS payload.

The launch of UARS was delayed by the Challenger accident; new NASA safety rules also required the redesign of the CLAES instrument which had used a solid hydrogen cryogen. UARS was finally launched on September 15, 1991

CHLORINE MEASUREMENTS

Within a few months after launch, the UARS MLS instrument was able to map ClO (chlorine monoxide - an ozone destroying radical) within the Arctic vortex showing the extent of ClO formation and its close association with polar stratospheric cloud formation [1]. Prior to this mapping, knowledge of the ClO build up in the Northern Hemisphere had come from the two polar aircraft missions. Not only was the UARS measurement an important confirmation of earlier aircraft results, but it also showed the extent of the zone of elevated ClO. Since these initial observations, UARS has continued to monitor both the Arctic and Antarctic late winter-spring ozone depletions. The UARS data have shown that northern hemisphere ozone depletion in January-March 1997 is the largest ever measured.

At the time of the launch of UARS, some scientists speculated that the ozone destroying chemicals within the polar vortex would leak to mid-latitudes. Other scientists argued from a hydrodynamical perspective that containment of the chemicals must occur. Scientists on the HALOE team were the first to notice very low concentrations of the long lived trace gas methane in the center of the spring Antarctic polar vortex [2]. Analysis showed that very low values of methane exist within the mid and upper stratosphere in late fall and these values descend to the lower stratosphere by late spring, a net descent of 12-15 km over six months. These measurements were confirmed by the UARS CLAES later by model calculations [3]. The unmixed descent of long lived trace gases requires a very isolated polar vortex system. Thus it was not until the launch of UARS and the mapping of long lived gases whose distributions reveal patterns of transport by the winds that chemical containment of the vortex could be demonstrated.

Despite decades of measurements and observations, a few vocal critics of anthropogenic ozone loss theory have continued to argue ozone loss is natural. Some have argued that the heavy chlorofluorocarbons molecules will never rise into the stratosphere. Instead, the high levels of observed stratospheric chlorine are due to volcanic activity. UARS has made a number of measurements that refute these ideas. UARS CLAES has detected large amounts of both CFC13 (F11) and CF2Cl2 (F12) in the stratosphere proving that these chemicals can easily get into the stratosphere [4]. Furthermore, as the chlorofluorocarbons are broken down in the stratosphere, they release chlorine and fluorine which form hydrogen fluoride (HF) and hydrogen chloride (HCl). HF is a long lived trace gas with no important natural stratospheric sources. UARS HALOE has detected HF and HCl in the stratosphere and found that both gases are increasing at the same rate as the CFCs are increasing in the troposphere with about a 5 year lag time [5]. This would not occur if chlorine came from intermittent volcanic sources.

The long lifetime of the UARS mission has led to some remarkable trace gas trend information. One of the more dramatic observations has been the vertical transport of water vapor upward in the tropical stratosphere. The amount of water vapor entering the stratosphere changes throughout the year as the tropical tropopause gets colder and warmer. These variations in water vapor ascend slowly into the stratosphere and appear coherent to about 30 km (from 16 km) [6]. The water vapor observations tell us that the tropical region must be relatively isolated from the rest of the stratosphere or these variations would be diluted.

REFERENCES

[1] J.W. Waters, "Microwave Limb Sounding," in Atmospheric Remote Sensing by Microwave Radiometry, edited by M. A. Janssen, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1993.

[2] J.M. Russell, J.M., III, A.F. Tuck, L.L. Gordley, J.H. Park, S.R. Drayson, J.E. Harries, R.J. Cicerone, and P.J. Crutzen, "HALOE Antarctic observations in the spring of 1991," *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 20, 719-722, 1993.

[3] G.L. Manney, W.A. Lahoz, R.S. Harwood, R.W. Zurek, J.B. Kumer, J. Mergenthaler, A.E. Roche, A. O'Neill, R. Swinbank, and J.W. Waters, "Lagrangian transport calculations using UARS data, Part I: Passive tracers," *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 3049-3068, 1995.

[4] R.W. Nightingale, A.E. Roche, J.B. Kumer, J.L. Mergenthaler, J.C. Gille, S.T. Massie, P.L. Bailey, D.P. Edwards, M.R. Gunson, G.C. Toon, B. Sen, and P.S. Connell, "Global CF2Cl2 measurements by UARS/CLAES: Validation by correlative data and models," *J. Geophys. Res.*, UARS special issue, 101, 9711-9736, 1996.

[5] J.M. Russell, III, M. Luo, R.J. Cicerone, and L.E. Deaver, "Satellite confirmation of the dominance of chlorofluorocarbons in the global stratospheric chlorine budget," *Nature*, 379, 526-529, 1996.

[6] P.W. Mote, K.H. Rosenlof, M.E. McIntyre, E.S. Carr, J.R. Holton, J.S. Kinnersley, H.C. Pumphrey, J.M. Russell III, J.W. Waters, and J.C. Gille, "An atmospheric tape recorder: The imprint of tropopause temperatures on stratospheric water vapor," *J. Geophys. Res.*, 101, 3989-4006, 1996.

UARS Instrument	Measurement	Primary Objectives	Status
ACRIM - Active Cavity Radiometer Irradiance Monitor	Total solar irradiance	Trends in total solar irradiance	operational
CLAES - Cryogenic Limb Array Etalon Spectrometer	Ozone, chlorine nitrate, nitric acid, nitrous oxide, methane, water, aerosols, N ₂ O ₅ , NO, NO ₂ , CFC11, CFC12, temperature	Observe ozone, nitrogen and chlorine reservoir species in the stratosphere	mission completed May 5, 1993
HALOE - Halogen Occultation Experiment	Ozone, water, methane, aerosols, HCl, HF, NO, NO ₂ , temperature	Observes trends in stratospheric ozone, methane, water and the products of chlorofluorocarbon photolysis	operational
HRDI - High Resolution Doppler Imager	Mesospheric, stratospheric winds, aerosols	Observe stratospheric and mesospheric winds	operational
ISAMS - Improved Stratospheric and Mesospheric Sounder	Ozone, aerosols, CO, methane, nitric acid, nitrous oxide, NO, NO ₂ , N ₂ O ₅ , temperature	Observe ozone, nitrogen radical and reservoir species	failed July 1992
MLS - Microwave Limb Sounder	Ozone, water, chlorine monoxide, nitric acid, temperature	Observe ozone, water, and chlorine monoxide radical	water vapor radiometer failed April 23, 1993 otherwise operational
PEM - Particle Environment Monitor	Energetic particle flux, xray backscatter, magnetic field	Observe high energy particles that would influence atmospheric chemistry	operational
SOLSTICE - Solar Stellar Irradiance Comparison Experiment	Solar UV spectra	Provide long-term measurements of solar ultraviolet and far-ultraviolet radiation at the top of the Earth's atmosphere	operational
SUSIM - Solar Ultraviolet Spectral Irradiance Monitor	Solar UV spectra	Provide long-term measurements of solar ultraviolet and far-ultraviolet radiation at the top of the Earth's atmosphere	operational
WINDII - Wind Imaging Interferometer	Mesospheric and thermospheric winds	Observe winds in the mesosphere and thermosphere	operational